

Information System Design Smart Building Management System with Rapid Application Development Method and Laravel Framework

Muhammad Wildan Alfatih
Electrical Engineering
Sebelas Maret University
Surakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- The information system is an important thing for the continuity of the smart building management system because all the functions of the system are collected into one container, namely an information system. The designed information system has the function of monitoring energy use, controlling electrical energy in buildings, monitoring temperature and humidity, and conducting security monitoring. In making the information system using the rapid application development method so that development can be completed quickly and the use of the Laravel framework is intended to facilitate the development of information systems. Thus the information system created can be completed quickly and can fulfill the main function of the smart building management system information system.

Keywords:- Energy, Control, Monitoring, RAD, Laravel.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of technology in modern times has increased human needs, especially in terms of comfort in a building. Where in realizing this, humans use smart building systems to increase comfort. This was also followed by the engineering faculty of the eleven March university in Indonesia, which implemented a building management system in one of its buildings. Where in the building monitoring the use of electrical energy, security systems, and other supporting devices is carried out. However, all of these systems have not been integrated and connected to each other so that in practice it is considered impractical. Thus an information system is needed that can accommodate all of these functions so that the ease of use of the system can increase. In addition, it is necessary to provide additional control of electrical energy remotely in order to increase the efficiency of the use of electrical energy in buildings.[1, 2, 3, 4]

In its manufacture, the information system uses the rapid application development method or commonly abbreviated as RAD so that the developed system can be completed quickly and according to the needs of the building manager. RAD itself has three main stages, namely the planning stage, the development stage and the implementation stage. The use of the Laravel framework was also chosen because of the ease of development where the Laravel framework has the MVC concept, namely models, views and controllers. In use, work related to the database will be controlled by models and controllers. Inside the

model will be added commands to manipulate the database. While the controller is used to map the data in the information system. And the view will be used to make the user interface display of the information system. [5, 6, 7, 8]

II. PROPOSED METHOD

A. Planning Stage

This stage aims to analyze the system objectives and identify the need to achieve the goals of the system. The purpose of the Smart Building Management System information system is to display information in the form of energy, temperature, humidity and security data that is easily understood by users of the Smart Building Management System information system. In addition, the designed system must be able to provide different functions for each user based on the level of account used. The type of account level in question is the user, admin, and developer account levels.[5, 7]

Fig. 1: Data Flow Diagram

B. Development Stage

The architecture of the smart building management system can be seen in the image above. The figure shows that there are five different types of devices, namely digital KWH meters, temperature and humidity sensors, fire sensors, security cameras, lighting controls and energy control panels. Where the digital KWH meter will read the value of voltage, current, frequency, active power, reactive power and real power from the electrical energy used. The reading data will be sent to the information system using

the Teensy microcontroller and the HTTP Post method. Data for temperature and humidity will be sent using the ESP32 microcontroller and the HTTP Post method. For fire sensors, the information system will receive information from sensors sent via ESP8266 and using the HTTP Post method. For security cameras, it is enough to do a live broadcast via the IP address of the security camera used. Meanwhile, to control the lighting control and energy panel control, we will use the HTTP Get method and use the ESP8266 microcontroller. [9, 10]

Fig. 2: Arsitekturkomunikasi SBMS

The designed Smart Building Management System information system has three types of account levels, namely user, admin and developer accounts. Where the user account level can only see the data displayed on the information system, the admin account level can control the hardware that is integrated with the information system and add accounts, and the developer level can access all data from the smart building management system information system. [11]

Fig. 3: Use case diagram

C. Implementation Stage

The Implementation stage is the stage of implementing an information system that has been developed based on the objectives of the information system development. Besides that, in the implementation stage, users and developers will test the information system first before it is implemented in the building as a whole.

III. RESULT

A. Energi MonitoringPage

This page is a page that displays information about energy which is divided into current card usage, electricity price, energy usage, this month cost, previous month cost and status. The Current Usage Card displays information on the amount of energy being used in real time, while the Electricity Price Card displays electricity prices in kWh units. Card energy usage displays information of today's total usage and current month's total usage. Information that displays today's total usage is marked with the name Today while information that displays today's total usage is marked with the name This Month. The Card This Month Cost provides information regarding costs that need to be incurred this month which refers to the energy used this month, while the Card Previous Month Cost provides information regarding costs that need to be incurred in the past month which refers to the energy used last month.

Fig. 4: Energy Monitoring 1

On this page there is also information in the form of values of voltage, current, frequency, active power, reactive power and apparent power. Where this information will only appear if the visitor to the smart building management system is an admin or developer so that visitors with user access cannot see information on the value of voltage, current, frequency, active power, reactive power and apparent power.

Fig. 5: Energy Monitoring 2

B. SecurityMonitoringPage

This page is a page that can display a list of security cameras used and integrated with the smart building management system information system. This page can also display live views from security cameras if the camera used has a feature for live viewing or mirroring. If the camera does not have this feature which causes the live view to not appear on the smart building management system information system, the information system can redirect the user to the security camera live view page.

Fig. 6: Monitoring CCTV

The Fire Alarm page shows the status of the fire sensors used in the Smart Building Management System. When there is no page fire it will show status OK. Meanwhile, when a fire occurs, the page will display an alert status and a switch will appear to reactivate fire safety on the Smart Building Management System. This page can also display all fire sensors used in the Smart Building Management System.

Fig. 7: Monitoring Fire Alarm.

C. TemperatureandHumidityMonitoringPage

This page is a page that can monitor and record temperatures connected to the smart building management system information system. The latest temperature value will be displayed at the top of the page and at the bottom there is a graph that displays the temperature recording data that has been read by the system. The temperature data is stored in the MYSQL database. This page can also display the latest temperature data from all temperature sensors used in the system. The temperature recording graph displayed on this page is the temperature that has been read by the temperature sensor since the sensor was first integrated with the information system. The graph displays the temperature measurement values with a period of every 60 seconds where the time period is the time period that has been set on ESP32 to take temperature readings once every 60 seconds. In its application, the user can see the results of

recording temperature within a certain period of time by utilizing the range feature in the graph. So that the user can see the results of recording the temperature according to the desired time period. There is also a feature to download temperature recording data in xlsx format and csv format so that users can download temperature recording data from the information system.

Fig. 8: Temperature and Humidity Monitoring

D. Energi ControlPage

The energy control page is a page that is used to activate or deactivate panels and electronic devices used in the smart building management system. This page can only be accessed by admins and developers because this page can control the system so that visitors with user access are not allowed to access the energy control page.

Fig. 9: Control Energy

IV. CONCLUSION

The smart building management system information system created using the RAD method and the Laravel framework can monitor energy use, temperature, humidity, fire sensors and security cameras and control electrical energy remotely.

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